

Uniformity and Bias of Derangement Representations for Continuous Metaheuristics

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Abstract

Continuous metaheuristics can tackle derangement problems by decoding real-valued vectors directly into fixed-point-free permutations. This work analyzes two rejection-free derangement representations: an existing post-hoc fixed-point correction method and a novel sequential construction approach. Both always produce valid derangements, yet they induce non-uniform, biased sampling of the derangement space. We characterize and quantify this bias, and demonstrate on two derangement problems that decoding uniformity has a practical impact on optimization performance.

CCS Concepts

• **Theory of computation** → **Evolutionary algorithms**; • **Computing methodologies** → *Bio-inspired approaches*; • **Computing methodologies** → Continuous models.

Keywords

Combinatorial Optimization, Derangement Representation, Continuous Metaheuristics, Differential Evolution

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1 Introduction

Combinatorial optimization (CO) problems, including, for example, the Travelling Salesman Problem and the 0-1 Knapsack Problem, are often NP-hard, making exact methods practical only for small instances [9]. Nature-inspired metaheuristics offer scalable alternatives [3] but their application to CO is not straightforward. Structured solution spaces typical for CO problems require indirect encodings or specialized evolutionary operators. Random-key (RK) encodings [2], which represent permutations as real-valued vectors decoded by sorting, have become the de facto standard, enabling continuous metaheuristics such as Particle Swarm Optimization [14] and Differential Evolution [21] to operate directly on permutation problems.

However, the application of continuous metaheuristics to *derangement problems*, where solutions must not contain fixed-points, i.e., $\forall \pi_i \in \pi : \pi_i \neq i$, has been explored only recently [16]. Treating derangements as permutations with additional constraints is inefficient. It forces search over the full permutation space, which is roughly e times larger than necessary, and requires constraint handling or multi-objective problem reformulation. Encoding derangements directly via permutation-to-derangement mappings avoids this overhead entirely [16]. This work analyzes the bias introduced by such mappings, quantifies deviations from uniformity, and proposes a novel decoder with reduced bias.

2 Permutations and derangements in continuous metaheuristics

RK encoding [2] is the standard indirect permutation representation in continuous metaheuristics. An n -permutation is represented as a vector $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and decoded by sorting. The rank order of the elements after sorting defines the permutation. RK guarantees valid permutations and introduces smoothness and locality in the search landscape. Small perturbations in \vec{x} yield gradual changes in permutation space, facilitating effective gradient-like exploration [4]. This redundancy also provides a neutral search space that can mitigate deceptive problem structures [17].

However, RK encoding covers all n -permutations, which makes it prone to generating infeasible solutions when searching for constrained permutations such as derangements. Derangements arise naturally for example in combinatorics [26], graph theory [6], and cryptography [1], and appear implicitly in any permutation problem that forbids self-assignment. Tackling derangement problems by constrained optimization methods introduces substantial overhead. Penalty-based constraint handling techniques require careful tuning of the penalty coefficient [8]. Multi-objective reformulations avoid the tuning problem but impose a high additional computational cost [7].

Whether infeasible solutions help or hinder search is fundamentally landscape-dependent. Empirical evidence shows they are essential on some problems but harmful on others [25]. This problem-dependence can be avoided entirely by restricting search to derangements only, eliminating constraint handling and focusing the optimization budget exclusively on feasible solutions [22].

2.1 Post-hoc correction

The DER algorithm [16] maps permutations produced by continuous metaheuristics to derangements via a post-hoc correction. Fixed-point pairs are in this approach eliminated by mutual swapping, and any remaining odd fixed point is exchanged with the

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permutation’s lowest or highest value, guaranteeing a fixed-point-free result.

DER significantly reduces the search space: the number of n -derangements satisfies $!n = n!/e$ [23], limiting the search to approximately 37% of the full permutation space. At the same time, it adds only $O(n)$ overhead and, as a deterministic post-hoc correction, largely preserves the landscape characteristics of the underlying RK search space [2, 4, 16].

However, DER introduces a non-uniform mapping. Different permutations can decode to the same derangement with unequal preimage sizes, meaning not all derangements correspond to equal volumes of the continuous search space. Such decoding-induced bias is known to affect sampling distributions in other RK-based encodings [4]. This can be harmless, or even helpful, when high-quality solutions happen to be overrepresented. However, in the general case, or when the optimum lies in an underrepresented region, it may mislead the search.

2.2 Derangement decoding by sequential importance sampling

Several methods for generating uniform random derangements exist [18, 19], including rejection sampling (expected cost $e \approx 2.718$ permutation draws per derangement), recursive cycle-based algorithms, sequential importance sampling, and restricted transposition schemes. Rejection sampling is unsuitable for decoding real-valued vectors in continuous metaheuristics, as a variable number of random draws would disrupt the fixed-dimensional search space structure. Rejection-free methods, on the other hand, require a fixed number of pseudo-random draws that can be deterministically substituted by continuous vector components, making them natural candidates for derangement decoding.

Here, we introduce SIS+, a sequential derangement decoder closely related to the Sequential Importance Sampling (SIS) algorithm [19]. SIS+ constructs derangements sequentially by choosing, at each position, an unused value that is not a fixed point. The key extension over standard SIS is an explicit recovery mechanism for the final position. Standard SIS ends, with probability $O(1/n)$, with a fixed-point at the last position. SIS+ handles this case by swapping the value with a randomly selected earlier position, guaranteeing a valid derangement in all cases. While this recovery may marginally increase non-uniformity, it is a necessary condition for practical use as a derangement decoder and does not compromise the algorithm’s advantage over DER in terms of sampling bias.

The core idea of SIS+ is to construct the permutation sequentially. At each position, i , assign a value π_i such that: i) π_i has not been assigned to any previous position (is permutation), ii) $\pi_i \neq i$ (has no fixed point). The algorithm constructs for each position, i , a set of candidate values that satisfy both constraints, $\mathcal{C}_i = \{c \in \{0, \dots, n-1\} : c \notin \{\pi_0, \pi_1, \dots, \pi_{i-1}\} \wedge c \neq i\}$. Then, the value of π_i is selected uniformly from \mathcal{C}_i using the i -th element of \vec{x} as a random source. This continues until the $(n-1)$ th position which always has only one candidate remaining. If this candidate is $n-1$, a fixed point would be created. This fixed point is eliminated by swapping it with a randomly selected position from the previously constructed derangement. Full outline of SIS+ is provided in algorithm 1.

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Input:  $\vec{x} \in [0, 1]^n$ 
Output: fixed point-free  $\pi = (\pi_1, \pi_2, \dots, \pi_n)$ 
Initialize  $\mathcal{U} \leftarrow \emptyset, c \leftarrow 0$  // set of used values, index into  $\vec{x}$ 
for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $n-2$  do
     $\mathcal{C}_i \leftarrow \emptyset$  // build  $\mathcal{C}_i$  from unused values excl. the fixed-point,  $i$ 
    for  $v \leftarrow 0$  to  $n-1$  do
        if  $v \notin \mathcal{U} \wedge v \neq i$  then
             $\mathcal{C}_i = \mathcal{C}_i \cup \{v\}$ 
        end
    end
     $c_{\text{idx}} \leftarrow \lfloor x_i \cdot |\mathcal{C}_i| \rfloor$  // draw valid candidate,  $c$ , from the candidate set  $\mathcal{C}_i$ 
     $c \leftarrow \mathcal{C}_i[c_{\text{idx}}]$ 
     $\pi_i \leftarrow c$  // assign  $c$  to the  $i$ th position
     $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{U} \cup \{c\}$  // mark  $c$  as used
end
 $c \leftarrow$  the one remaining unused value // exactly one value remains unused
if  $c \neq n-1$  then
     $\pi_{n-1} \leftarrow c$  // no fixed point
else
     $\pi_{n-1} \leftarrow c$  // avoid fixed point by swapping with random position
     $c_{\text{idx}} \leftarrow \lfloor x_{n-1} \cdot (n-2) \rfloor$  swap( $\pi_{c_{\text{idx}}}, \pi_{n-1}$ )
end
return  $\pi$ 
    
```

Algorithm 1: Sequential importance sampling with final-position repair (SIS+).

2.3 Uniformity of DER and SIS+

Although SIS+ has a higher computational complexity than DER ($O(n^2)$ vs. $O(n \log n)$), it achieves a fairer derangement representation. Since both decoders are biased by design, their uniformity was assessed computationally: for $n \in \{4, 5, 6, 7, 8\}$, each decoder was applied to $50 \cdot n$ random vectors from $[0, 1]^n$, and the resulting derangement frequency histograms were analyzed via minimum, maximum, CV, and χ^2 statistics (see table 1).

Both decoders are, as expected, statistically non-uniform. DER is slightly closer to uniform at $n = 4$, but SIS+ achieves lower CV and χ^2 for all tested $n \geq 5$. These results confirm SIS+ as the fairer decoder for analyzed derangement sizes.

3 Experimental evaluation

The practical impact of both decoders was evaluated on two derangement problems.

3.1 Test problems

The *affinity maximization problem* (AMP) [16] models a scored Secret Santa assignment. Given pairwise affinities among n people, $\text{aff} : \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$, the goal is to find the derangement, π , maximizing the cost function, $\text{AFF}(\pi) = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{aff}(\pi_i, i)$, $\forall i : \pi_i \neq i$. Problem instances were constructed from 11 weighted social networks, including Freeman’s EIES network [11], the Cross-Parker intra-organizational network [10], the Les Misérables co-appearance network [15], and eight Star Wars character interaction networks [12], yielding problem dimensions from $n = 18$ to $n = 110$.

The *invigilator assignment problem* (IAP) looks for an assignment of invigilators (proctors) to university exams [20, 24]. Given a fixed exam timetable, the considered version of IAP seeks a one-to-one assignment of invigilators to exams that respects the derangement constraint and period-based invigilator availability while minimizing the number of student-enrollment overlaps between each invigilator’s home course and assigned exam. An IAP instance consists of a set $E = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ of n exams, a set I of n invigilators,

n	Histogram size (n)	Random trials	DER				SIS+			
			Min, Max	σ	CV	χ^2	Min, Max	σ	CV	χ^2
4	9	450	33, 71	12.2746	0.245	27.12	21, 91	19.1717	0.383	66.16
5	44	2200	28, 124	21.5733	0.431	409.56	24, 106	17.9811	0.360	284.52
6	265	13250	20, 157	18.8943	0.378	1892.08	21, 123	18.0619	0.361	1729.04
7	1854	92700	20, 251	20.8896	0.418	16180.8	18, 132	17.3464	0.347	11157.2
8	14833	741650	16, 283	20.8546	0.417	129021	10, 150	17.2433	0.345	88206.4

Table 1: Derangement encoding uniformity analysis.

Instance	Exams (n)	Periods	Avg. $ A_i $
yue20013	26	6	3
yue20023	38	6	3
yue20011	126	18	3
yue20012	141	18	3
yue20021	162	21	3
yue20022	182	21	3
yue20031	174	18	3
yue20032	210	18	3

Table 2: Test IAP instances.

indexed by their *home course*, $h(i) = i$, sets $S(e)$ of students enrolled in exam $e \in E$, a function $t : E \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, T-1\}$ assigning each exam a time period, and sets of available time periods, $A(i) \subseteq \{0, 1, \dots, T-1\}$, for each invigilator. In a typical IAP instance, A_i is a contiguous interval or a small number of consecutive periods around the invigilator’s home exam period. The goal of IAP is to find an assignment that assigns each invigilator to a course other than her/his home course, satisfies the availability constraints, and minimizes student-enrollment overlap.

Formally, IAP can be formulated as a search for a derangement, π , minimizing the weighted cost function, $IAP(\pi, \alpha) = \alpha \cdot O(\pi) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot A(\pi)$. In this function, the term $O(\pi) = \sum_{i \in I} |S(i) \cap S(\pi_i)| / N_{\text{total}}$ represents student-overlap normalized by the total number of student enrollments, N_{total} , the term $A(\pi) = |\{i \in I : t(\pi_i) \notin A_i\}| / n$ evaluates normalized availability violations, and $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ balances the two. This IAP formulation has been applied to real and synthetic exam timetabling instances from the Yeditepe University dataset [20], described in table 2.

3.2 Experiments and results

All AMP and IAP instances were solved using j2020 [5], an advanced Differential Evolution variant selected on the basis of preliminary experiments in which it outperformed standard PSO, global-best PSO, PSO with 6 informants, vanilla DE, L-SHADE, and IMODE. Each configuration used a population of 100 vectors and a budget of 10^7 fitness evaluations. The IAP weighting parameter was set to $\alpha = 0.2$. Both derangement decoders were compared against vanilla RK encoding as a baseline (RK-produced solutions with fixed points are naturally penalized by both fitness functions so this comparison is possible). All instances were solved independently 50 times to account for stochastic variation.

The results of the experiments are summarized in table 3 and table 4, respectively. They were analyzed using nonparametric tests [13], treating independent runs across encodings as independent samples. We used Kruskal-Wallis tests ($\alpha = 0.05$) followed by Dunn-Holm pairwise comparisons and Cliff’s delta effect sizes. An encoding was considered superior only when all pairwise tests (adjusted $p < 0.05$, favorable median, positive effect size) favored it. Otherwise, the outcome of the comparison was deemed inconclusive.

The tables clearly illustrate the usefulness of derangement evolution (DER outperforming baseline RK on the majority of AMP and IAP instances) and the positive effect of encoding with lower bias (SIS+ matching or significantly outperforming DER on all but 2 AMP and all IAP instances).

The convergence plots in fig. 1 and fig. 2 further support these findings. SIS+ not only matches or exceeds DER and RK in final solution quality, but consistently leads throughout the majority of

Instance	n	RK		DER		SIS+	
		Avg	Max	Avg	Max	Avg	Max
Cross	46	158.12	166	159.24	173	160.18	168
Freeman’s	46	106.10	111	106.33	112	109.69	116
Les Miserables	77	244.67	263	252.22	272	261.37	282
[†] SW Episode 1	37	151.16	153	151.73	153	148.47	150
[†] SW Episode 2	32	92.92	93	92.96	93	91.18	92
SW Episode 3	24	88	88	88	88	88	88
SW Episode 4	20	102	102	102	102	102	102
SW Episode 5	19	115	115	115	115	115	115
SW Episode 6	18	82	82	82	82	82	82
SW Episode 7	24	104	104	104	104	104	104
SW Episodes 1-7	110	449.76	484	463.08	479	488.75	506

Table 3: AMP results. Instances where SIS+ was statistically better than or tied with other encodings are shown in bold. [†] marks inconclusive results. Higher is better.

Instance	n	RK		DER		SIS+	
		Min	Avg	Min	Avg	Min	Avg
yue20011	126	0.17	0.20	0.19	0.21	0.13	0.16
yue20012	141	0.20	0.23	0.20	0.24	0.15	0.17
yue20013	26	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
yue20021	162	0.24	0.26	0.24	0.27	0.18	0.21
yue20022	182	0.24	0.28	0.26	0.29	0.21	0.23
yue20023	38	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
yue20031	174	0.21	0.24	0.23	0.25	0.18	0.20
yue20032	210	0.27	0.29	0.26	0.29	0.21	0.23

Table 4: IAP results. Instances where SIS+ was statistically better than or tied with other encodings are shown in bold. Lower is better.

the search process. This highlights the practical value of reduced decoding bias for the investigated problems.

4 Conclusions

This work studied two rejection-free derangement decoders for continuous metaheuristics: the existing DER (post-hoc fixed-point correction) and the proposed SIS+ (sequential construction with final-position repair). Both guarantee valid derangements but induce non-uniform sampling of the derangement space with different characteristics.

For practical problem dimensions ($n \geq 5$), SIS+ provides more balanced derangement coverage than DER, as evidenced by consistently lower CV and χ^2 statistics. Empirical validation on AMP and IAP confirmed that this reduced bias translates into measurable optimization gains. SIS+ matched or significantly outperformed DER on the majority of tested instances and exhibited superior convergence throughout the search. Future work should examine the

Figure 1: Convergence plots for AMP instances. Lines show mean fitness \pm 95% CI. Higher is better.

Figure 2: Convergence plots for IAP instances. Lines show mean fitness \pm 95% CI. Lower is better.

scalability of SIS+ to larger problem dimensions and its applicability to other constrained combinatorial problems where decoder uniformity may play a similar role.

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